

Pokémon: 20 Years with Pikachu and Friends (Updated for the 2026 30th Anniversary)

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Good day, readers. Once again, we are celebrating an anniversary in the world of video games: Pokémon is having a birthday. It has now been three decades since Game Freak released the first instalment of a role-playing game series that would become a landmark in popularity and sales. Thanks to this franchise, Nintendo gained another major driving force. On 26 February 1996, the company launched the first Pokémon game in two different versions: *Green* and *Blue*. In Spain, they would not get to enjoy this game until 1999, in its *Red* and *Blue* editions —the *Green Edition* was never released outside Japan, except in Latin America, where the *Blue* version was renamed *Green*.

Pokémon is extremely popular, particularly among children, often overlooked by many adults due to its “childish” aesthetic —or rather, for its “for all audiences” appeal. Despite this, we should not forget —and I speak to all video game enthusiasts here— the tremendous importance this franchise had for Nintendo, as we will see below. The series faced a tough struggle just to come to life, and Pokémon reflects the efforts of its creative team to develop it, ultimately catapulting them to undeniable commercial success. I will provide a brief overview of the franchise here, although a much more detailed entry may follow later.

It all began when Satoshi Tajiri, a native of Tokyo who was initially going to study engineering, created a fanzine —a fan publication, by fans, for fans— about video games called Game Freak in the 1980s. He later decided to embark on a different venture: creating video games. During this period, while working on his self-published magazine, he met Ken Sugimori, who would become the artist designing the first Pokémon and a lifelong friend of Tajiri, initially collaborating by illustrating the magazine.

Satoshi Tajiri, video game designer. Creator of Pokémon and current executive producer of the franchise.

Satoshi Tajiri never worked as an engineer; instead, he began as a video game tester for industry magazines, and this experience increased his desire to create his own games. Tajiri also wrote two books, which helped him develop the idea of a deeper script for a new video game, beyond the typical action/adventure games of the time. A passionate fan of arcade games —both physical arcade machines and home games inspired by them— he and Ken Sugimori felt that video games were increasingly lacking in storytelling and originality.

Satoshi Tajiri drew inspiration for Pokémon from his own childhood

Tajiri spent his childhood surrounded by nature, as his home was on the outskirts of the city. Notably, he developed unusual interests for a typical child and an exceptional ability to focus on a single subject, which proved invaluable in his career as a game designer. For years, this led some to mistakenly believe he had Asperger's syndrome. From his early hobbies, he transferred his passion for entomology —the study of insects— into Pokémon, inspiring features such as the rival class “Bug Catcher,” who specialises in training bug-type Pokémon.

Tajiri believed that children today, constantly immersed in a world of technology, stress, and work, could benefit from disconnecting and using that technology for fun that also conveyed positive values. Video game consoles fascinated him because of this potential. For this reason, he saw in Shigeru Miyamoto, the creator of Mario, both a rival and a mentor to follow.

His commitment to Japanese youth and his personal experiences is evident in the design of the first game's Kantō region, which is slightly based on the real Kantō region in Japan. This approach continued in later games, with regions inspired by real-world locations such as Europe, the United States, and others.

Real Kantō region in Japan, and to its right, the Kantō of *Pokémon Red* and *Blue* —Green—

When the Game Boy project was approved and later released, Tajiri became fascinated with this portable console and its ability to connect players with each other. He realized that interactions could go beyond mere competition —such as exchanging items or characters, and later, battling together against other opponents. Ultimately, he finalized the concept of what would become Pokémon and presented his idea to Nintendo, which approved the project. Unfortunately, despite receiving the “yes,” the company did not fully understand it until Shigeru Miyamoto arrived. Miyamoto already knew Tajiri through his work at Nintendo —Tajiri had contributed to Mario, Wario, and Yoshi spin-offs, which facilitated collaboration and cohesion on these projects—.

But... what are the core premises of Pokémon?

Tajiri’s idea was to create an RPG —role-playing game— that broke away from the typical, mostly adult-oriented schemes —fantasy, characters fighting in dungeons, levelling up, etc.—. In this game, players wouldn’t have to “kill” their opponents, only defeat them through tactics and friendly combat. Tajiri believed that death was a concept that shouldn’t appear so easily in a game intended for children.

Everything revolved around Pokémon —the name of the series derives from the contraction of the words Pocket Monsters— creatures based on real-world fauna and flora, some on mythological beings —mainly Eastern, like the Pokémon Ho-oh—, and others inspired by human devices or artificially created —giving rise to Pokémon such as Porygon or Mewtwo.

Both Tajiri and Miyamoto were fascinated by the idea that in a portable console, players could capture and collect creatures that were also “portable” within the game world, since Pokémon are captured using Poké Balls, which allow them to be easily transported. Players form bonds with these characters, which roam through various zones and present different levels of difficulty to defeat and capture. Pokémon appear in different locations and, later on, under additional factors that increase the challenge of collecting them all.

All this occurs alongside the exploration factor and interaction with non-player characters, who narrate the story while challenging the player to Pokémon battles, giving items, etc. Pokémon make up the fauna —and part of the flora— of the fictional universe. They function both as companions —players can even participate in contests of talent and beauty with their Pokémon, and feed or care for them virtually—, as food, avatars of deities, and some are even responsible for the creation of the Pokémon world.

Their fundamental role for the player is to fight in battles on behalf of their trainers. This was the most ingenious aspect of the franchise, allowing users to decide their team and organize it according to the Pokémon types they face —types divide Pokémon into categories such as Fire, Water, Fighting, Flying, etc., with elemental abilities that are effective or not against other types.

To add a Pokémon to their team, players must first defeat it in battle with their own Pokémon —though they cannot completely weaken it, as it will faint and cannot be captured—. This acts as a constant test against opponents, proving the player worthy of commanding the Pokémon. The player becomes like a conductor of their team, appearing as a character in the game rather than managing protagonists from the shadows, as in most RPGs.

This idea would later be echoed by Intelligent Systems in games such as *Fire Emblem: Awakening* in 2012 —where the protagonist can be customised by the player and represents the player within the game—. Additionally, each Pokémon captured can be renamed by the player, adding a personal touch and affection for the Pokémon —a feature also seen in other RPGs, such as *Final Fantasy* games, which allow the user to rename their protagonists.

All this provides a sense of freedom within a pre-established storyline while offering a continuous path of learning and growth for both the player and their team, which contributes to the game's addictive and enjoyable nature. Statistics are carefully managed, further enhanced by Pokémon breeding —introduced in the *Gold* and *Silver* editions in 1999. The original Pokémon protagonist —Red— was later named Satoshi in the anime in honour of Tajiri, and is one of the selectable names for the player.

The creators also paid tribute to their friendship and respect for Miyamoto by including both names as options for the player. Shigeru would be the grandson of the guide in the game, Professor Oak —originally called Green/Blue, and later Gary Oak in international versions. Players can choose a different name if desired, with the original protagonist and rival names being Red and Green (Green in the Japanese edition; Blue in international editions).

Players embark on a journey to become the greatest Pokémon Trainer in the world, capturing all Pokémon to complete the Pokédex, an encyclopaedia developed by Professor Oak. To progress and win battles against both wild Pokémon and trainers, players must assemble their preferred team, train them, care for them, and face other trainers, including Gym Leaders —places where humans who raise Pokémon for battle train them and accept challenges from trainers worldwide. After defeating these leaders, the ultimate goal is to challenge the Pokémon League, led by the Elite Four —top trainers who, once defeated, grant the title of Pokémon League Champion.

The animated version of Professor Oak introduces players to the first major choice in Pokémon: selecting a starter Pokémon from three options—in the first release, *Red/Blue/Green*: Bulbasaur, Squirtle, and Charmander, of Grass, Water, and Fire types, respectively—. Here comes a bit of irony: my first choice, back in 1999, was Bulbasaur, although I lost that game and later chose Charmander, whom I named Eufrasio. Even though my favourite type is Water—in my *Pokémon X/Y* safari, incidentally, Water-type Pokémon appear—Charmander is my favourite of the three starters, and I still own a Charmander plush from 1999.

Additionally, Professor Oak's grandson—the professor was originally named Dr Yukinari Okido—constantly challenges us to battles, serving as the protagonist's eternal rival—choosing starter Pokémon that counter ours—, always seeking to defeat the player. The final battle after the Pokémon League's Elite Four is, in fact, against him, and once again he will be a step ahead of the protagonist, having already defeated the Elite Four beforehand.

Once defeated, the gameplay experience does not end there. After the credits, players can continue capturing the Pokémon they have yet to obtain—including Mewtwo, which can only be caught after defeating the League—, continue training their Pokémon as long as they wish, and even challenge the Elite Four at any time to earn more money and experience for their team. Pokémon managed to blend fantasy with a dose of reality and contemporaneity, offering an experience of eternal growth, constant struggle, and an insatiable drive to always strive for more. For completionist players, these games are a real triumph.

The unforgettable soundtrack, still considered among the best in Nintendo's catalogue, was composed by Junichi Masuda, who has been with the company since its foundation, contributing to the music for *Mendel Palace*—originally *Quinty*, released in Japan in 1989—, a puzzle game for Nintendo. Masuda not only composed music but, being a programmer by profession, also collaborated across development teams, particularly in sound design. Later, he became director of some entries in the series and also served as a producer.

Masuda even influenced the creation of new regions for the franchise, such as Hoenn, inspired by Kyūshū Island, where he spent his summers as a child. His work is evident in the iconic soundtrack of the early Pokémon games.

Game Freak —relaunched in 1989 as a video game developer— nearly went bankrupt during Pokémon’s creation, but Tajiri did not give up —five employees left the company, and Satoshi Tajiri even went without a salary, relying on his parents’ financial support to complete the project—. He also secured financial backing from Creatures Inc., a Nintendo subsidiary. Pokémon’s development ultimately lasted six years —far longer than usual at the time, especially for a portable title, which typically took weeks, sometimes months, and rarely years.

Finally, both versions were released in 1996, as previously mentioned. Europe received them much later —in 1999— in two special editions: *Red* and *Blue* —the Japanese releases were also reissued as *Red* and *Blue*, special editions of *Red* and *Green*—. This was followed by another special edition, *Pokémon Yellow*, in 1998 —released in Spain as *Pokémon Amarillo*—, which adapted the plot of the Pokémon anime —Ash Ketchum was the protagonist, Satoshi in the Japanese game and original anime version, and the starter Pokémon he would receive was Pikachu, as in the anime—.

Covers of the *Red* and *Blue* editions of Pokémon. Original illustrations by Ken Sugimori.

Pokémon breathed new life into the legendary Game Boy

Although Nintendo did not create the first handheld console which stored its games in cartridges —that honour belongs to Milton Bradley’s MicroVision, released in 1979— it was the company that managed to make such devices popular with the general public and establish them permanently in the market. This success is thanks to Gunpei Yokoi and Satoru Okada’s nearly indestructible Game Boy, a console that marked a turning point in the market. The device enjoyed great commercial success, but as is often the case with any technological product, its sales eventually declined, and the limited creativity of developers in providing innovative titles also became apparent —though it never stopped receiving remarkable games.

Between Yokoi's idea of launching a new version of the console in 1996, called the Game Boy Pocket, and the massive success of Pokémon for Nintendo that same year, the console soared once again. The first *Pokémon* sequel —the *Gold* and *Silver* editions— was released in 1999 in Japan, the same year that *Green (Blue)* and *Red* reached Europe. Factors such as avoiding overlap with the Japanese releases and the usual delays in bringing games from Japan to other countries meant that these new entries were delayed in Europe until 2001.

They say sequels are never as good as the original titles, but this was not the case with this game, which took everything that made the previous release great and refined it. Today, it remains the Pokémon iteration offering the most content —though not necessarily the largest number of catchable Pokémon, as new ones are created for each subsequent release. *Gold* and *Silver* repeated the success of the first generation —*Gold* and *Silver* are known as the second generation, while *Red* and *Green (Blue)* form the first generation of Pokémon.

Controls, graphics, and sound effects were improved —for example, incorporating stereo sound—, new Pokémon animations were added, new types were introduced —further expanding strategic diversity—, and a day-and-night cycle was implemented, meaning certain Pokémon could only be caught at specific times. Additionally, there was a fantastic surprise: players could revisit almost the entire Kantō region from the original 1996 *Pokémon* game, defeating the Gym Leaders of that area once more —Blue/Gary/Green would be the Gym Leader of Viridian City after Giovanni's defeat in the first games.

For the most devoted fans, the greatest surprise in this edition lay in the true final battle: a duel against the protagonist of the first Pokémon game, Red —now presented as a lone wolf, a semi-hermit trainer— a fight that breaks the fourth wall while achieving an epicness rarely seen in the franchise, leveraging nostalgia and putting the player against their “former self”. In *Pokémon Red/Green (Blue)*, we faced our childhood rival, but *Gold* and *Silver* went further, taking the concept a step forward: you had to defeat yourself.

The moment when Gold —the protagonist of *Gold* and *Silver*— comes face to face with Red, the protagonist of the first Pokémon game, in *SoulSilver* and *HeartGold*, the 2009 remakes of *Gold* and *Silver*.

It is the most beloved instalment among series enthusiasts —for some, the first generation will always be the most complete, and for others, the third— and it received a 2009 remake for the Nintendo DS, which also included a physical device in the game box: a pedometer called the PokéWalker, allowing players to interact with their console by sending Pokémon from their team to the device to level them up as it was used as a pedometer.

The overwhelming success of Pokémon went far beyond the games

And Pokémon did not stop there. Not with its second instalment, nor by limiting itself to the video game sector.

In 1997, Tajiri and the other members of the creative team produced the Pokémon animated series, created by the studio OLM —Oriental Light and Magic— responsible, for example, for the first animated adaptation of *Berserk* in that same year. The series continued to air with new seasons following the adventures of Ash —Satoshi— as the protagonist of all versions until 2023 —in each Pokémon game, the protagonist is different—. The series also included original storylines —as in any animated series usually based on manga, where filler episodes are necessary while the mangaka advances the original manga publication; in this case, being based on video games, it offered narrative filler while new Pokémon game releases came to market.

Considered too childish by many fans, the Pokémon manga —which later had its own OVA adaptation— followed exclusively the games' plot and was somewhat more serious in tone, making it a much more successful adaptation of the original video game storyline into another medium. In Spain, the original manga, *Pokémon Special*, first published in 1997 and edited in the country by Norma Editorial, has been available for years. Its publication was one of the surprises at the past XXI Barcelona Manga Fair.

Giovanni, as he appears in the *Pokémon Special* manga. He is the leader of the criminal organisation Team Rocket, both in the original video games and in this manga; a criminal mastermind who plans to make money through casinos and the enslavement of Pokémon for his own purposes. Thanks to the protagonist's actions, he apparently retires from organised crime.

Pokémon also has its own trading card game, *Pokémon Trading Card Game* —released in October 1996 in Japan, known in Spain as *Pokémon: Juego de Cartas Coleccionables*—, which in turn inspired a video game based on the card game itself (*Pokémon Trading Card Game*, released in 1998 for the Game Boy). The original card game continues to be played and supported even today, in 2026 —the date this article was reviewed— by Game Freak.

We could also enjoy video games for home consoles, such as *Pokémon Stadium* in 2000 —purely focused on Pokémon battles—, which additionally allowed interaction with the handheld consoles, enabling Pokémon to be transferred from the Game Boy to the Nintendo 64 via an accessory. These purer video games were later joined by various spin-offs, such as *Pokémon Snap* —a 2000 game centred on photographing Pokémon—; and it gave rise to series where the player would directly control the Pokémon, like *Pokémon Mystery Dungeon*, whose latest release, *Pokémon Mystery Dungeon: Rescue Team DX*, came out in 2020 for the Nintendo Switch, starting this collection of games in 2005.

It is also worth noting the immense number of products related to the franchise, with Pikachu being one of the most iconic and widely reproduced characters in contemporary popular culture. In Japan, there are even planes, trains, and buses inspired by the adorable Electric-type rodent, voiced by seiyū Ikue Ōtani. There are countless figures and plush toys for young children, in many variants, both official and unofficial, as well as a wide range of collector figures for older fans.

Game Freak’s franchise even has its own line of aeroplanes since 1998, operated by All Nippon Airways. This particular aircraft is a Boeing 747-400D, announced in 2004. Inside, passengers are treated to an experience fully themed around the Pokémon saga, with visual elements extending even to the aeroplane’s headphones, paying homage to the Pokémon brand.

All this merchandising is complemented by Nintendo's recent Amiibo collectible figures, which allow fans not only to decorate their homes with these endearing creatures, but also to interact with various video games such as *Super Smash Bros. for Nintendo 3DS* and *Super Smash Bros. for Wii U* (2014), as well as *Smash Bros. Ultimate* (2018) for Nintendo Switch. Pokémon has released canonical titles for every generation of Nintendo handheld consoles since the Game Boy, the latest being *Pokémon X and Y* (2013), *Pokémon Omega Ruby* and *Alpha Sapphire* (2014 remakes of the 2002 Ruby and Sapphire games), and *Pokémon Sun* and *Moon* (2016), along with their special versions *Ultra Sun* and *Ultra Moon* (2017).

Following these, *Pokémon: Let's Go, Pikachu!* and *Let's Go, Eevee!* were released for Nintendo Switch in 2018—reimaginings of the first generation with simplified mechanics for younger players, utilising a special Poké Ball-shaped controller. Later came *Sword and Shield* (2019), *Brilliant Diamond* and *Shining Pearl* (2021, remakes of the fourth-generation Diamond and Pearl, originally for Nintendo DS in 2006), and *Pokémon Scarlet* and *Violet* (2022).

Respecting the content of the originals, these releases also added extra story chapters and incorporated modern mechanics, such as stereoscopic 3D in certain 3DS titles, dual-screen functionality, Pokémon horde battles, and other new features. In 3DS editions, players could stealthily approach Pokémon to catch them rather than always engaging in random battles, a mechanic also used to update classic titles.

Alternative series have continued alongside the mainline games, such as Pokémon Legends, with *Arceus* (2022) and *Z-A* (2025), both for Nintendo Switch. The mainline Pokémon series has remained largely consistent—perhaps overly so—given the challenge of innovating over thirty years without straying from the elements that make the franchise iconic. Nevertheless, it has adapted to the technical improvements of each new console, improving graphics and increasing variety in Pokémon training, though Switch titles have faced criticism for comparatively modest graphics and performance issues.

Appropriate use of hardware is evident in Nintendo DS titles, where dual screens allowed battles to display on the top screen while command options appeared on the bottom. In *X* and *Y*, battles and other scenes could be viewed in stereoscopic 3D, with the game fully rendered in a polygonal environment. Several recent editions also allow players to customise their protagonist—a feature absent in earlier Pokémon titles, though removed in remakes such as *Omega Ruby* and *Alpha Sapphire* to respect the originals.

20th Anniversary Promotions

To celebrate Pokémon's twentieth anniversary, GAME stores in Spain distributed the legendary Pokémon Mew free of charge, a psychic-type Pokémon and one of the original 151 from the 1996 releases. Nintendo was not done there: on 26 February 2016, the company held a special Nintendo Direct show dedicated entirely to Pokémon, broadcast live at 15:00 UCT, and launched a commemorative official website in several languages, including Spanish, detailing various events and announcements. Original Pokémon films were made available on iTunes, and the Pokémon anime series could also be accessed via 3DS/2DS consoles through the Nintendo Anime Channel.

30th Anniversary Promotions

Currently, the official Pokémon anime series is available in multiple languages on the official Pokémon TV channel on YouTube, including English and Spanish. To celebrate Pokémon's thirtieth anniversary in 2026, Nintendo and Game Freak organised various special activities and releases highlighting the franchise's continuity and relevance. These included commemorative editions of classic games, new Pokémon Trading Card Game events, and exclusive digital content on official platforms, aimed at collectors and players of all ages.

For example, the European International Championship was held in early 2026, featuring games such as *Pokémon Go*, *Scarlet* and *Violet*, and *Pokémon Unite*—a multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA) released in 2021. *Pokémon Go*'s “Which is Your Favourite?” feature allowed players to pose with their preferred Pokémon and share images on social media using #Pokemon30 without needing an account. Interactive events “Day with Pokémon” and “Night with Pokémon” were also organised, designed to bring together the global trainer community. Day events offered family-friendly activities, while night events included surprises and content for veteran fans.

These celebrations demonstrate how Pokémon remains a global cultural phenomenon, combining nostalgia with new experiences, and showing that thirty years after its debut, it continues to unite generations of players and collectors worldwide. Further details are available on the official 30th-anniversary website. Also, *Pokémon Pokopia*, a game developed by The Pokémon Company and Game Freak, with the help of Omega Force was launched on 5 March 2026, as part of the anniversary celebration.

Official artwork from *Pokémon Omega Ruby* and *Alpha Sapphire*

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Kotaku, Nintendo Ibérica, Pokémon, Official website for the 20th Anniversary of Pokémon, Bulbapedia | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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